

Integration in Central Asia: Process and State

Jamaldinov Hakim Khatamovich

Department of World History, Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

Abstract: *The article analyzes the status of the Central Asian republics and the role of the region in the global integration process, the stages of integration, the features of interstate cooperation at the regional level, the history and prospects of the relationships between the republics, various formats of the integration phenomenon, regional interstate associations, the essence of foreign policy relations, and new perspectives on the economies of the Central Asian republics.*

Keywords: *Central Asia, integration, reintegration, Single Economic Space, Central Asian Union (CAU), Central Asian Economic Community (CAEC), Organization of Central Asian Cooperation (OCAC).*

Integration (from Latin “integration” – “restoration”, “supplement”, “connection”) is the process of combining parts into a whole. Depending on the context, it may refer to political, systemic, social, economic, ecological, and other types of integration.

Karl Deutsch views integration as a means by which conflicts between states can be peacefully resolved when there are stable mutual expectations among them. Thus, he saw integration both as a state and as a process. Integration as a state is better considered as a political community.

The economic role and prospects of Central Asia are not yet fully recognized in the world. To a large extent, due to inertia, the region is still not perceived by the international community as a significant player on the economic map of the world. However, the region is changing, and today its role must be reassessed. The Central Asian states have made significant progress in their development over the past twenty years. The share of Central Asia in the global GDP based on purchasing power parity has increased by 1.8 times since 2000. The states have achieved economic stability and have serious growth prospects. The aim of this report is to form a new perspective on Central Asia as a major and dynamically developing region.

Achievements and structural changes in the region

Growth from 2000 to 2021		2000	2010	2021
Population (million people)	1,4x	55	62	77
GDP (billion dollars)	7,5x	46	243	347
Share in global GDP by PPP, %	1,8x	0,4	0,6	0,7
Accumulated volume of FDI, billion dollars	17,2x	12,3	101,6	211,4
Foreign trade turnover of goods, billion dollars	6x	27,4	149,4	165,5
Mobility of the population, passenger-kilometers per capita	3,1x	2198	4435	6792

Throughout history, integration, as a process or state, has developed in the region both vertically and horizontally, as well as from the top down or from the bottom up, taking on different forms and paces. The issue of integration in Central Asia can be divided into the following stages:

1. As a political integration process – “Unified Economic Space” (Central Asian Union – CAU, from 1998 Central Asian Economic Community – CAEC, and from 2001 Central Asian Cooperation Organization – CACO) from 1993 to 2005.
2. As an integration state – from 2005 to 2016.
3. Re-integration (from Latin “re” – “renewal”, “repetition” and “integration” – “restoration”, “supplement”, “connection” – the process of reuniting previously disintegrated entities) since 2017.

The first stage – the practical embodiment of integration can be viewed as the establishment of the Central Asian Union (CAU) consisting of Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan. The Central Asian states occupy an exceptionally important geostrategic position on the Asian continent, with crucial land and air communication routes passing through their countries. The region is endowed with vast energy resources (the Caspian Sea with its oil and gas reserves), deposits of ore and metallurgical raw materials, and precious metals.

One of the most serious problems is the unresolved issue of water usage. Its resolution will lead to sustainable development in the region, as the socio-economic well-being of the Central Asian states depends on water and its distribution. Another issue is the reliable energy supply of the region, where a unified energy system has been functioning for decades, dominated by the hydropower plants of Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan, with Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan as the main gas suppliers.

In the mid-1990s, as a potential solution to the problem of relations between the irrigation and energy sectors and irrigation, the idea of creating an International Water-Energy Consortium (IWEC) was proposed.

The initial developments of the idea to create the IWEC date back to the decision of the Intergovernmental Council (IGC) of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Uzbekistan on July 24, 1997, which led to the formulation of a Concept on the principles of cooperation between Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Uzbekistan for the establishment of international consortia, approved by the IGC on December 12, 1997.

Based on the conclusions of the Intergovernmental Commissions (IGC) in 1997-1998, the Council of Prime Ministers (CPM) of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, and later Tajikistan made a series of decisions regarding the establishment of the IWEC.

Currently, there is an approved Concept for the establishment of the International Water and Energy Consortium (IWEC) by the Council of Heads of State members of the Organization for Central Asian Cooperation, and a number of draft Intergovernmental Agreements (IGA) have been developed for the creation of the IWEC.

However, in 2001, the Central Asian Economic Community (CAEC) became the Organization for Central Asian Cooperation (OCAC). By 2005, the OCAC was dissolved.

Although this stage was characterized by the adoption of ambitious projects, they did not come to fruition. There are several reasons for this:

firstly, in defiance of the alliance between Russia, Belarus, and Ukraine (the so-called “Slavic Union”), the creation of a self-sufficient regional organization in the post-Soviet space faced challenges;

secondly, after the collapse of the union economic infrastructure, economic integration among the republics did not occur due to the different economic reforms implemented in the Central Asian republics;

thirdly, although it was initiated as an economic integration process, political goals ultimately took precedence;

fourthly, the process was used as a diplomatic platform;

fifthly, the political ambitions of the region's leaders played a significant role.

In 2005, the head of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, officially announced the cessation of multilateral relations in the format of the Central Asian Cooperation Organization (OCA) and a shift towards bilateral cooperation among the republics of the region.

Thus, the integration process transitioned into an integrative state, characterized by a multi-vector foreign policy both in general and at the regional level.

Currently, Uzbekistan's new foreign policy approaches have emphasized the necessity of regional cooperation and created a more optimistic atmosphere in Central Asia. Much of this progress can be attributed to the efforts of Uzbekistan's President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, which have led to significant results in the interaction among all five states. Since 2017, relations among the countries in the region have been normalizing. Previously distant nations are increasingly coming closer and reaching agreements, with even the more isolated Turkmenistan becoming involved in Central Asian cooperation.

Water resources are a vital strategic and closely interdependent factor in Central Asia. They are linked by the common river basins of the Syr Darya and Amu Darya, a unified ecological system, and a shared line of gas pipelines from Gazli to Bukhara, Tashkent, Shymkent, and Almaty. The countries in the region possess significant proven reserves of gas, oil, coal, and uranium. There are also renewable energy sources. An industrial base has been established for the extraction of energy resources and electricity production, sufficient for the stable economic development of all Central Asian countries.

The creation of a robust transportation infrastructure in Central Asia amidst the high dynamics of international relations, not only at the level of individual countries but also regionally, is a strategic issue. Special attention should be given to maximizing the utilization of Central Asia's transit and logistics potential through the proactive development of transportation infrastructure, both in the direction of Uzbekistan-Turkmenistan-Iran-Oman and Uzbekistan-Kyrgyzstan-China. In this regard, Uzbekistan's initiative to hold an international conference in Tashkent in 2018 titled "Central Asia in the system of international transport corridors: strategic perspectives and untapped opportunities" deserves full approval.

Currently, important issues such as Uzbekistan's access to the Caspian Sea through Turkmen ports, a 37% increase in trade turnover with Kazakhstan, the opening of road checkpoints "Okoltin" and "Malik" at the Uzbek-Kazakh state border, the establishment of entrepreneurial communities between the border regions of Central Asian countries, and the achievement of agreements on the demarcation and delimitation of borders are being successfully addressed. Turkmenistan has opened new railway and road bridges connecting Turkmenabad and Farab across the Amu Darya. This is a significant section of the transport and transit route Uzbekistan-Turkmenistan-Iran-Oman.

An agreement has been reached to expedite the construction of the Uzbekistan-Kyrgyzstan-China railway. A pilot automotive run along this corridor has already been conducted. Air communication with Tajikistan has been resumed. It is essential to continue effectively utilizing the transit and logistics potential of the region and to develop transportation infrastructure, attracting funds from the international capital market to create a unified transport system TRASEKA, which will provide new access to Middle Eastern and global markets.

In the current period of globalization, Central Asia, with its rich natural resource reserves and important strategic position, is increasingly becoming a center for the intersection of political and economic interests of world powers. The complexity of the region's countries entering global politics can be attributed to several factors, including a lack of adequate experience and the objective necessity of constantly balancing between various centers of power in accordance with national interests.

REFERENCES:

1. Bartlett, D.L. (2001) Economic Development in the Newly Independent States: The Case for Regionalism. *European Journal of Development Research*. (2001) Vol. 13. No. 1.
2. EDB (2008) Water and Energy Resources in Central Asia: Utilization and Development Issues. EDB Industry Report no. 2.
3. Emerson M., Vinokurov E. (2009) Optimisation of Central Asian and Eurasian Trans-Continental Land Transport Corridors. EUCAM, Working paper 07, December. Available at: www.ups.be and www.eabr.org
4. Vinokurov E. (2009) Mutual Investment in The CIS Banking Sector. *The Euromoney Central Asia & CEE Financial Markets Handbook 2009*. 10, Euromoney, pp. 4-9.
5. Вардомский Л.Б. (2005) Центральная Азия и Закавказье в глобальном и региональном контекстах политико-экономического развития. Мальгин А.В., Наринский М.М. (ред.) Южный фланг СНГ. Центральная Азия-Каспий-Кавказ: энергетика и политика. Москва: Навона. с. 18-3.
6. ЕАБР (2010) Система индикаторов евразийской интеграции. Алматы: ЕАБР. Доступно на: www.eabr.org/rus/publications/projects
7. Головнин М.Ю. (2008) Проблемы и перспективы интеграционной группировки ЕвразЭС, Евразийская экономическая интеграция. 1: 27-44.
8. Головнин М.Ю. (2009) Перспективы совместного развития инфраструктуры фондовых рынков. Евразийская экономическая интеграция. 1 (2): 41-48.
9. Звягельская И.Д. (2005) Центральная Азия: эволюция параметров безопасности и стабильности. Мальгин А.В., Наринский М.М. (ред.) Южный фланг СНГ. Центральная Азия-Каспий-Кавказ: энергетика и политика. Москва: Навона. с. 32-46.
10. Либман А.М., Зевин Л.З. (2009) Интегрирующееся региональное пространство: дополнительные возможности экономического роста. Евразийская экономическая интеграция. 2 (3): 68-88.
11. Лузянин С.Г. (2005) Центральная Азия: факторы развития. Мальгин А.В., Наринский М.М. (ред.) Южный фланг СНГ. Центральная Азия-Каспий-Кавказ: энергетика и политика. Москва: Навона. с. 68-86.
12. Парамонов В., Строков А., Столповский О. (2008) Россия и Китай в Центральной Азии: политика, экономика, безопасность. Бишкек: Общественный Фонд Александра Князева.
13. Савкович Е. (2006) Проекты экономической интеграции Китая и Казахстана. Агентство политических новостей - Казахстан. 2006. 28 августа.
14. Ушакова Н.А. (2004) Современное состояние и перспективы Организации центральноазиатского сотрудничества. *Проблемы постсоветских стран*. 6: 203-219.
15. Винокуров Е.Ю., Либман А.М., Максимчук Н.В. «Динамика интеграционных процессов в Центральной Азии». *Евразийская экономическая интеграция*, №2 (7), май 2010.